

DISTORTIONS AND ITS PREDICTION OF SATELLITE COMPONENTS
MADE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS DURING THERMAL CYCLING TEST
IN VACUUM

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the thermal cycling test in vacuum on antenna parabolic reflector, its scaled model and specimen, made of two carbon fibre sheets and an aluminum honeycomb core, the approach for predicting the permanent distortion. During thirty thermal cycles between -180°C and 120°C , the temperature distribution and corresponding distortions were measured and some experimental data and charts were given.

On the basis of relationship between permanent distortion and thermal cycling number of times, we present mathematical model in terms of power function. Using this model permanent distortion and service life in long term under thermal cycling can be predicted based on a few data.

INTRODUCTION

When a satellite flies in orbit, the extended components, for example antennas, solar panels etc, will undergo severe temperature environment. The long service life geostationary satellites would even withstand over thousands of thermal cycles.

It is the problem of great concern that the distortion of parabolic antenna occurs under above severe temperature environments. As regards the solar panels and external support component, their fatigue damages are also concerned about, besides distortions and dynamic problem. All these problems are important for their design and application. Due to the limitation of satellite mass and in order to meet the space environment and functional performance requirements, the above extended components are mostly made of composites such as carbon fibre and Kevlar, which have higher specific strength and lower expansion coefficient than other materials. With the development of material science, the proportion of composites being used in satellites is getting larger and higher. The broadcasting satellite being developed would utilize a great quantity of structure made of composite materials. In the course of developing and designing application satellite with long service life and high reliability, the problem which must be solved first is to predict the permanent distortion and the fatigue damage of composite components under the cold and hot cycling condition.

TEST DESCRIPTION AND MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The main problem of concern is the thermal distortion (Including the transient distortion and the permanent distortion). This paper studies only the permanent distortion of the component. We selected three kinds of specimens, as shown in Fig.1 to Fig.3.

Fig. 1 Reflector in the chamber

Fig. 2 The scaled model of the reflector and specimens placing on the heat sink in the chamber.

Fig. 3 The specimens of carbon fibre sheet sandwich structure.

The full scale reflector nanging in the chamber is illustrated in Fig.1. Which is practically one of the spareparts. It is sandwich structure consist of two carbon fibre sheets as skin and an aluminum honeycomb core cut obliquely from revolutionary paraboloid.

Fig.2 shows a scaled model of reflector, placed on the heat sink in the chamber. It is a prototype with the size of 400mm x 250mm x 12mm.

Fig.3 shows two sandwich coupon specimens made of two carbon fibre sheets as skin and aluminum honeycomb as the core.

The above three specimens were simultaneously put in the chamber of two meters in diameter and experienced thirty thermal cycles measuring their temperature and strain distribution respectively. The practical temperature cycling range were as follows:

For the full scale reflector, between -144°C and $+116^{\circ}\text{C}$.

For the scaled model of reflector, between -165°C and $+119^{\circ}\text{C}$.

For the strip specimens, between -168°C and $+117^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Recording the strain variation processes during the first ten cycles in more detail, it has been found that the repeatability after five cycles was better than before and the strain curves rose steadily. During preceding cycles the composite materials were unstable under thermal vacuum condition due to moisture and volatile composition and shrinkage strains were very large. It corresponds with test results observed in China and in other countries¹⁻³.

The chamber pressure was less than 10^{-3} Pa during the test. The liquid nitrogen and infrared heating cage were used to carry out the temperature cycling between low temperature -180°C and high temperature $+120^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The temperature measurements were completed by means of thermocouples, while its data acquisition, processing and recording were made by DACQ-2F(Date Circuit Check Meter) and Great-wall 0520A micro computer. The temperature measurement error was $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The strain measurements were made by means of SND120-10AA-4 strain gage. These curves were modified and data were processed by selecting quartz glass for calibration. The error of strain measurement was $\pm 50\mu\epsilon$ ^{1,2}.

The measured results of the permanent distortion of the three type of specimens, during thirty temperature cycling are shown in Fig.4. As can be seen from these data and curves obviously, negative strains occurred during the first several cycles. This phenomenon results from escaping of moisture and volatile composition typically. It is one of the features of this kind of composites which is different from metal material.

Fig.4 Relations between the permanent distortion and the numbers of temperature cycles.

MATHEMATIC MODEL AND PROCESSING METHOD

In order to predict the permanent distortion of the components made of composite in space cold and hot environments, the relationship between permanent distortion and number of thermal cycles can be described by following mathematical model of power function

$$E_y = A(N_x - N_{x0})^b \quad (1)$$

where E_y -permanent distortion, in terms of strain or displacement.

N_x -the number of thermal cycles between two temperature extremes.

N_{x0} -the number of thermal cycling for preprocessing the composite materials after it was shaped, which serves as the initial point of the test and depends upon the type of material.

A,b-constant, generally determined by the least square method based on measured data.

The test data shown in Fig.4 are drawn on the double logarithmic paper. It can be seen from Fig.5 that they are approximately three straight lines, as shown in Fig.5, namely:

$$\ln E_y = b \ln(N_x - N_{x0}) + \ln A \quad (2)$$

Choosing $N_{x0}=3$, and $N_x=10,15,20,25,30$, the values A and b were calculated respectively, and were listed in Table 1.

The mathematical model (1) could also be expressed as:

$$N_x - N_{x0} = A^{-\frac{1}{b}} E_y^{-\frac{1}{b}} \quad (3)$$

We use equation (1) and (3) for predicting respectively permanent distortion and thermal cycling numbers in normal service, as shown in Tables 2 and 3. As can be seen from these Tables, for the full scale reflector, all the values A and b are nearly consistent with average values \bar{A} and \bar{b} ,

Fig.5 Logarithmic relations between the permanent distortion and the temperature cycle numbers

while other values differ slightly great. However, all the permanent distortion predicted from Table 2 tends to be safe. When the number of thermal cycles is 500 or 1000, the permanent distortions of the scaled model are 14% or 17% bigger than average values, while the predicted permanent distortions of the honeycomb sandwich specimens are 7% bigger than average values. It follows from above that using the test data of fifteen cold and hot cycles, we can predict the distortion or service life under

thermal cycling conditions.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The temperature cycling test in vacuum made on the three kind of specimens. The cycling number being 30, showed that the measured permanent distortions was not large. After the tenth cycles the permanent distortions had a tendency of steady increase.
2. A large quantity of tests have proved that the permanent distortions of the composite materials under vacuum temperature cycling condition are positive, namely in tension. Because the severe cold and hot cycling in vacuum can cause the escaping of moisture and volatile composition and the weakening of internal connection, resulting in microcrack at interface and fraction of individual fibre.
3. The temperature cycling test of the satellite components made of composite materials should be performed under vacuum. The reason is that the distortion results from synergistic effect of both vacuum and thermal cycling. It cannot be replaced by temperature cycling test under ambient pressure.
4. From the analysis based on practical test measurements, this paper gives mathematical model for predicting permanent distortion or cycling life. It is believed by comparison that the prediction is reliable using the data of preceding fifteen cycles. Even for complex composite structures, 24 cycles of qualification test as stipulated by MIL-STD-1540B may not be necessary⁴. For the acceptance test of the flight type product the cycling test may be made only from 8 to 10 times and the results can be predicted.
5. Data processing of component made of composite materials is different from that of component made of normal single materials. Due to the effect of volatile composition and environmental moisture in forming process the preceding several cycles, such as 3 to 5 cycles, are considered as for preconditioning and should be deducted depending upon the specific condition.
6. If the future antenna reflector is bigger than that now being used, the temperature cycling test in vacuum would be performed on scaled model instead of real product, but it should be made of identical material, using same shaping technology and processing method.

REFERENCES

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Table 1 The parameter values estimated from the measurement data

Measured specimens	Expression				b	1/b
	$b = \text{Ln} \frac{E_{yi}}{E_{y10}} / \text{Ln} \frac{N_{xi}-3}{7}$					
	15	20	25	30		
(a)	0.338	0.338	0.339	0.336	0.338	2.96
(b)	0.1826	0.1456	0.1389	0.1393	0.1516	6.60
(c)	0.0881	0.0727	0.0598	-	0.0735	13.6

Measured specimens	Expression				A	A ^{-1/b}
	$A = E_{yi} (N_{xi}-3)^{-b}$					
	15	20	25	30		
(a)	103.6	103.6	103.5	104.1	103.7	1.08x10 ⁻⁶
(b)	203	218	221	221	216	3.91x10 ⁻¹⁶
(c)	607	625	641	-	624	9.67x10 ⁻³⁹

- (a) Full scale reflector.
- (b) Scaled model of reflector
- (c) Carbon cloth sandwich specimens.

Table 2 Predicted permanent distortion (μϵ)

Measured specimens	Mathematical model	-3 N _{xi}	50	100	500	1000
			(a)	$E_{yi}=104(N_{xi}-3)^{0.338}$	390	493
(b)	$E_{yi}=216(N_{xi}-3)^{0.152}$	391	435	556	617	
	$E_{yi}=203(N_{xi}-3)^{0.183}$	415	472	633	719	
(c)	$E_{yi}=624(N_{xi}-3)^{0.0735}$	832	875	985	1037	
	$E_{yi}=607(N_{xi}-3)^{0.0881}$	857	911	1049	1116	

Table 3 Predicted thermal cycles to distortion

Measured specimens	Mathematical model	E _{yi} (μϵ)	1000	2000
			(a)	$N_{xi}=3+1.08 \times 10^{-6} E_{yi}^{2.96}$
(b)	$N_{xi}=3+3.9 \times 10^{-16} E_{yi}^{6.60}$	2.46x10 ⁴	2.39x10 ⁶	
(c)	$N_{xi}=3+9.67 \times 10^{-39} E_{yi}^{13.6}$	614	7.59x10 ⁶	